

Using Realia to Improve English Vocabulary at Primary Level

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Abstract

The background of the study in this research is based on the phenomenon that students have difficulties in learning English vocabulary because the teacher teaches the vocabulary without being supported by teaching aids. The result is the students' ability to learn is slow. To improve students' ability in learning English vocabulary, teacher needs a strategy through using an aid that facilitates the students. Realia is one the aid that can be used in teaching English vocabulary. Using realia, students are able to learn English vocabulary easily. This research is aimed at finding the answers to the research questions and to achieve the objectives. This research is conducted in a classroom of a private school. With the help of Kempis and McTaggart model of research the data was collected and analyzed mathematically. The students were motivated with the use of realia. They gave full attention to teacher's explanation and showed great interest in learning new vocabulary. Finally, the result of this research shows that students' ability was improved after they were taught using realia. They were better in learning vocabulary.

Introduction

Vocabulary is the basic knowledge of any language. Furthermore, before the learning of other skills of English by the students, there are better opportunities for the students to master vocabulary. It is stated that vocabulary is the main aspect of English program, in middle school. The material is mostly concerned to master vocabulary. Vocabulary Mastering helps in understanding in communication written as well as oral. Obviously, vocabulary is the basis to learn other competencies including listening, speaking, reading and writing. Moreover, vocabulary needs to be taught at middle levels in schools. O'MALLEY, J. M., Chabot, A. U., & Kipper, L. (2001) stated that when student language learning is being provoked with the help of certain activities then they are at the stage of better understanding of the meaning of language. The interpretation of information with the help of realia strengthens the English language input comprehensively and makes it possible to create a relationship between the work and the classroom.

Realia is a term used in the field of education to refer to certain real-life objects. In vocabulary teaching, presentation of vocabulary with the help of realia actually means to bring real objects or something else which is being used in classroom for the illustration of vocabulary teaching, while in case of difficulty in interpretation of those objects which are not possible to use in classroom teaching, those objects can be replaced with maps, photographs of those materials or pictures etc. The rule is that, for concrete vocabulary and language realia plays important role, which also transforms a particular frame of reference. At beginning stage, realia considered to be fit as mostly the lesson material used in class is related to concrete items. The teacher is better able to polish the understanding of students with the help of realia, as realia transforms the saying into concrete form. New vocabulary is given a new life due to realia, and it enhances the student's chances to understand new words taught by the teacher. After having the experience of smell, taste and touch of the items, the remembering probability of students enhanced a lot. Any of the material that can be imagine, infect can be utilized for teaching vocabulary.

Current Scenario of Traditional Way of Teaching Vocabulary:

Observations revealed that the present teaching methodology of vocabulary is outdated, boring and not so much effectively or attractively provoke students. While in elementary schools English lesson main material is vocabulary. The important problem for the students is vocabulary memorization. They are not able to remember vocabulary meanings. The students are in a difficulty to write vocabulary. They mostly write words as they have heard. For example, some words such as classroom, chair, shoes and blackboard are being written as classroom, cheer, sues and blackbird. Moreover, they used to pronounce these in Pakistani pronunciation.

The observations taken at the preliminary stage showed the probable reasons why the difficulties may be faced in the classroom boring, dull and monotonous techniques create problems in this regard and students became bored and monotonous, resultantly they were lazy to learn. The students were learning vocabulary with the help

of teaching material and AV aids only by picking up pictures from the book and look at their dictionary meaning. There were no other teaching material or realia brought by the teacher for students' motivation.

Many methods can be used for teaching English to the children. In this regard, the adult person who is around the children specially the teacher plays a vital role in English learning capability of children. The teacher plays a vital role as children seek English firstly at school with teacher and spend more time to seek English with their teacher too. It is not the case for the English teacher to acquire the competence in English mastering but also to have the idea how to teach English to children keeping in mind the characteristics and development of children.

The world of children is concrete. Children better able to pick and understand things easier as compared to abstract. Elkind, D. (1967) stated that in elementary school the children mostly are at the concrete operation stages of development cognitively and therefore do not have the capability to think in abstraction. Same is the case with Piaget, he is of the view that every child has to face a series of stages before children got the ability to have logic and understand rationally in mature form. Four stages including sensory motor (birth to 18 months approximately) preoperational stages (2-7 years old), concrete operation (7 to 11 years approximately) and formal operation period (11 years onwards). In 4th grade of elementary school the children are 9 to 10 years old. They are included in concrete operational stages.

According to AL Qahtani, M. (2015) many ways are there to clear the meaning of a word, including visuals, realia, gesture and mime, give explanation or definition, conceptual questions, translation and give example. Teaching media and many techniques used to do vocabulary teaching also added by some experts. These teaching media and techniques can partially or in combined form be used. The researcher can use realia in teaching vocabulary keeping in view the characteristics and children's development lesson material for the students while referring the theories of teaching English for children specially about different teaching techniques of vocabulary for children. Children and adults have different learning characteristics. Moreover, children learn from concrete to abstract for example in English learning as foreign language. Just by saying words, they able to learn vocabulary. No doubt vocabularies are mostly on particular content word including verb, noun, adverb, adjective and daily routine simple expressions – in English for the first stage the vocabulary lesson often uses words for things and persons around the children for example girl, boy, body parts, furniture, house hold articles and stationary items etc. According to O'Malley, J. M., Chabot, A. U., Stewer-Manzanares, G. L. O. R. I. A., Russo, R. P., & Kipper, L. (1985) the reason why in the first stage of English such vocabularies are given to the students.

Objectives:

1. To describe the use of realia in teaching English vocabulary at primary level.
2. To provide students interest and involvement in the subject with the help of realia.
3. To describe the improvement of students' ability in learning vocabulary after they have taught using realia.
4. To prove that use of realia makes their vocabulary permanent part of their LTM.

Significance:

The activities that are provided by the realia are meaningful through deep experience during teaching and learning process. If realia are utilized to improve student's vocabulary mastery then it is very beneficial.

1. Student's prior knowledge will be elicited with the application of realia to go into real environment.
2. It can facilitate students to enrich their vocabulary and also motivate them in English learning.
3. It will give large feedback of knowledge about learning, applying and using realia especially for teaching vocabulary.
4. The study is also expected to have significant contribution to the development of language teaching theory, especially English teaching theory in the classroom through the use of realia as the instructional material to the public.

Research Questions:

1. How the implementation of realia is possible and effective in teaching vocabulary at primary level?
2. How can realia improve students' vocabulary learning ability?
3. Does teaching with realia increase motivation in students at primary level?

LITERATURE REVIEW:

Guthrie, M. (2017) state that a word set for a specific language or a word set that every language speaker might use. Likewise, Pearson, P. D., Hiebert, E. H., & Kamil, M. L. (2007) describe vocabulary as a words stock used by profession, class or person. Another definition, it refers to the words understood by, used by, or all common of specific person or group (www.en.wikipedia.org/wiki). In short, the words of a specific language that is used and understood by all speakers of the language is vocabulary.

Meaning has been associated by the vocabulary. Miller, G. A. (1995) defined vocabulary as a word's list with their meaning. Likewise, Ehri, L. C. (2017) states that it is the capability of recognizing words of individuals and with a specific letter combination, associate meaning from which a word is formed.

Vocabulary Aspect:

In vocabulary teaching, the aspect of vocabulary should be concerned by the teacher that really needs to be taught. Sweller, J. (1994) indicates many of the vocabulary aspects that should be taught to the students. They are following: -

Form: Spelling and Pronunciation:

The learner must have knowledge of what is the sound of a word like (its pronunciation) and how it is look like (its spelling). It should be made sure by the teacher that both aspects are correctly learned and presented.

Grammar:

If not covered by the rules of general grammar than the new items of grammar will need to be taught. There may be an unpredictable change of form in certain context of grammar that may are connecting with other words through idiosyncratic way in sentence. Providing information to learners is also important along with the base form teaching.

For example, while teaching a noun, plural form may also need to present, if irregular (mice / mouse), or for drawing attention of learners to the fact of having no plural at all (information, advice)

Collocation:

The arrangement and placement of words together by the specific combination of words is Collocation. In each context, sound's combination like "right" or "wrong" is made by Collocation. Few words may have some meaning, but they can't be combined uncertainly with same word. For example, throw and toss are two words having the same meaning and it can be said the toss a coin and throw a ball, but we can't use it as toss a ball or throw a coin.

Formation of Words:

Single idea that may be expressed in the form of a new vocabulary item consists of more than a single word. There are certain items of vocabulary formed by joining words (a noun and a gerund or two nouns etc.). For example, follow up, suit case, bookstore, whooping coup, swimming pool. For more developed learners it is very important to know how such words are combined or how particular words are constructed.

The Significance of vocabulary:

In our daily routine vocabulary is an important factor. In daily life we not only name things and incidents using words but also take help in expressing our thought with the help of certain words. Malcolm, N. (1954) stated that when we want to prove existence of anything or event for its recognition we have to name that particular thing or event otherwise it is hard to accept that thing, that incident or expression. Therefore, naming means we try to form structure and order the flux and chaos of existence that on the other hand would be a different sort of thing. We impose a meaning or an order by allotting names through which the world is being manipulated. Ariew, R. (1982) said, realia plays a connective role between language and the classroom. Realia has wider meaning specially in foreign language teaching interpretation.

Demonstration:

It is the physical interpretation of form, draft or outline of incidents or items in order to enhance the interest and knowledge of such things or incidents. Demonstration includes "depicting how" or "depicting what". While in some situations it also includes informing others about some things. It may not need verbal elaboration extensively. If verbal explanation is given by the teacher, then physical demonstration should not be accompanied with it. In demonstration the teacher can utilize the available classroom material and items and it is directed to the students to follow the teacher's instructions. The teacher may guide the students how they can demonstrate by their own in the class room.

Use the real thing / Realia

The teacher can use the real objects in order to clarify novel vocabulary and help to enter in the mind of students. Particularly for concrete objects, while explaining meaning, it is easier to show the object. The teacher may use the things present in the classroom like chair, blackboard, table, etc. Other which can possibly be seen across the window and other which can be brought in which needed. For example, when teaching about types of fruits, the pupils and teacher can take real fruits or something that can show them in the classroom.

Draw / Sketch

The teacher may draw or sketch anything on the board. The teacher can draw simple sketches which show meaning. It isn't a perfect drawing or sketch. A fast sketch with a few lines is enough.

Antonyms:

If the students have the knowledge of opposite, then a word can be easily defined. Mostly students ask "what is opposite of _____?" By comparing the meaning of a word with its antonyms the teacher can explain a word. Logical opposites in strict order are required for the explanation. The important thing is capability of students to understand the common and conceptual meaning of a word. For example, mostly it is easy to give interpretation of some rude rather than a polite expression.

Synonyms

Just like anonyms, it is particularly problematic to find a synonym which is simple enough to help the pupils. Penrose, R., & Merman, N. D. (1990) says that there's small point in simple providing additional new

word to illuminate the one the pupils doesn't understand. You don't all the time have to provide the pupils the word's general meaning. In this case, the pupils recognize what the teacher means, is the most important point. The pupils may comprehend the concept of it.

Verbal Interpretation:

In a variety of context, few language items are implemented effectively with the help of teacher. For example, situational illustrations and definitions are the best source of verbal explanation. De Jong, E. J., & Harper, C. A. (2005) say that teacher may utilize learner's own language for the explanation. Moreover, students' existing vocabulary knowledge for the meaning and definition in simple English can also be used by the teacher. For example, the world traffic may be interpreted by creating a situational setting. Cities are full of traffic. It is also harmful.

Translation:

A technique which converts into learners' own language is called translation. In monolingual translation me that is somewhat possible but it is hard to even translate into all the necessary languages in multilingual groups.

Following are some of them:

* The meaning may be derived when there is knowledge of existing words, especially if the word is in a paragraph.

For Example, _____ in autumn fall from the tree. From the sentence, the learners may complete the missing word of the sentence by creating a link between tree and autumn and conclude that a thing that mostly falls from the tree in autumn is leaf.

Picture and Flash Cards:

To demonstrate and make perfect or what we talk, the teacher can use flash cards, pictures, sketches and real objects. Things can be presented pictorially if the things are not easily carried or are unapproachable, they can. Images can take from illustrated advertisement in daily newspaper, photos or magazines. The cuttings or images can be fixed on card board to create a flash card.

Wall Charts:

Vocabulary presentation in a visual context with the help of wall charts is significant, unless and until it is visible clearly. Teacher and learners may perform activities with the help of wall charts, for example the vocabulary use, orally spelled, write pronunciation, and indicate the pointed thing. They learned it to explain wall chart part.

Word Activities:

Scrabble and Cross word puzzles are beneficial for revising and practicing vocabulary after it has been presented.

Teaching Tools for Vocabulary:

The word realia is derived from Latin, that is not the language of Romans, used as a native language of research, science and philosophy in most of the European countries by the scholars of Middle age. Since in Latin the plural of the secondary adjective of the adjective transforms it into a name, realia means the real thing, not words that are not considered "thing" or "real". For this reason, this word is plural "realia" (real), which, though, is not found in many Latin dictionaries, because they typically have classical rather than Medieval Latin objects.

The Features of Realia:

Realia provides language learners with multisensory language impressions, which, like Lucido, P. L., & Borabo, R. G. (1997), are recognized in part, at least by observation, entrainment, touch and manipulation of objects. Interaction with authentic materials helps in learning contextual grounding by connecting students to the language, as it is used in the target culture to meet the real needs of communication. Then use the realities; can improve the understanding of linguists, which are also prerequisites for real language learning.

Vinay, J. P., & Darbelnet, J. (1995) listed some features of realia. They are: -

- a. They are linked with the real objects.
- b. They are mostly more convenient and easier to approach as compare to the existing situation. They are usually economical and easy to use.
- c. They are noticeably large in number.
- d. They are multidimensional, and may fulfill many learning purposes or creative educational requirements.
- e. They are mostly understandable without language.
- f. They join fundamentals of training and creative and provoke the effective and cognitive fields.
- g. They can proceed from the common to the specific, or the reserve.

The Significance of Realia in Vocabulary Teaching:

For teaching students Realia is significant and useful. It is easy to show the objects than the verbal description of vocabulary in vocabulary teaching. Short, D. J. (2002) states with the interpretation of word meanings vocabulary can be learned more effectively, for example in teaching use of realia helps learners

involvement in direct experience. Learners can touch, smell, hearing the new words and see the items. When a thing is transformed from abstract to concrete, it makes easy for the learners to have deep rooted concepts.

Moreover, the learning process becomes more creative, lively and interesting by the use of realia. Learners' direct interaction with real objects enhanced the learners' positive results. Direct contact with the objects provides children long lasting learning according to Knowles, M. (1973).

Realia not only enhances the capability of learning vocabulary but also speeds-up the learning process and strengthens the memorized vocabulary effectively.

Tomalin, B., & Stempleski, S. (2013) pointed out further benefits of realia:

- a) They are not much costly.
- b) In addition, there is a series of sensory interpretation along with sight.
- c) They help in language development.
- d) They provide conceptual learning about color, size etc.

The Features of Young Learner:

Language learner is divided into three levels by Jackendoff, R. (1999) including beginner stage, intermediate stage and advanced stage. Every stage has its own features, teaching techniques and material.

The Sensory Motor Period:

From birth to approximate 2 years is the Sensory Motor Period. In this stage the cognitive development from infancy to older carried through the use of their senses and bodies as they discover the infants recognition, thinking and behaving sense about the incidents and items with eyes, mouth, hand and rest of the sensory motor elements in adaptive, assumed and organized way.

In this span of time in order to enhance cognitive development of children, adults including parents can play vital role by providing variety of items of different objects to the children. Infants may learn about their surrounding with the help of their senses. Resultantly, parents must arrange stationary, items including soft, hard, square, circular and toys. Children's cognitive development process can be enhanced by manipulating such common items.

It can be concluded that in this stage there is limited recognition development through personal experiences and senses of the children in their particular environment. Children are not in a position to categorize their experiences although they may recognize about the happening.

The Pre-operational Period:

From 2 to 7 years is the pre-operational period. In this period, in this period although a child can get symbol recognition but not able to interpret it mentally. Children between the ages of 2 to 7 are able to understand the outer existing world. They are better able to recognize their dependency at outer world. The characteristics of pre-operational stage are following:

- a) Child's ability to relate life to inert items is called Animism.
- b) Child's ability to accept and differentiate the original world is called Realism.
- c) Child's ability to suppose that everything is the outcome of human production is termed as Artificialize.
- d) The reasoning that is nor inductive or deductive is referred as Transudative reasoning. In an illogical way, reasoning ascends from important to further specific.

Teachers, by encouraging the execution of material can help the students to improve their achievements. The activities which improve their skills in English language are as follows:

- a) Deferred: Imitate some things or activities which they have seen in the past. For example, they may act like an animal they witnessed at the Zoo before.
- b) Symbolic Play: Pretending sleeping or being someone else is enjoyed by the children.
- c) Drawing: Children portray their mental condition into their drawings and paintings. Drawing encourages the children to speak about their art.
- d) Mental Image: Children can present objects and events but they can't anticipate any change in their mental thinking.
- e) Language: The adults surrounding the children provide them opportunities to talk with their elders and other people.

From the explanation above we can conclude that in this phase of time children are able to symbolize objects around them and realize the existence of them even when the objects are not around them.

Concrete Operational Period:

The concrete operational phase extends to 12 years of age from the age of 7. In this phase children are able to accomplish true mental system by overcoming the limitation of pre-operational thinking. Learners can limit their thinking and achieve actual mental operation. Students can perform mental activities only on objects that can be touched or seen. There are a lot of achievements in this phase.

- a) Reservation is the realization that anything essence remains unchanged although surface characteristics may change.
- b) Striation is the quality that arranges objects with respect to ascending and descending size.

- c) Taxonomy is the characteristic for the classification of objects with similarities placed in a wide category.
- d) The concept of numbers is the ability of a child which helps him to understand the meanings of the number.

When students reach this phase of cognitive development they are on the verge of being an adult through formal operation. An internal evolution occurs inside the children. At this stage their thinking becomes more logical and abstract they become more efficient in terms of memory and attentiveness as new strategies are developed in them. During the dealing with education implication, in this phase the students can accommodate and utilize the material they face, but only that which is tangible and concrete. As a result, total reliance on abstract subtleties can't be expected from them. From the explanation above we can conclude that in this phase of time children are able to make an accordance between their mind but are limited to concrete objects.

The Formal Operational Period:

The formal conductive phase during the start of abstract thinking commence at around 11 years of age. During this time young generation develops an ability to debate realistically on future and consider the possibilities that create doubts in their minds. At this stage, children start to search for relation and they test their mental ability by creating solution to their problem and feel comfortable with communication. Conclusively in this phase of time the great achievement of the students is the freedom from restrictions of the concrete objects.

In educational interpretation the children can be assisted by the teacher to construct general principle. These sorts of activities shall challenge the students' mentality but they should not be too difficult for them as it will frustrate them and cause failure.

We can conclude that in this period of time students, by using hypothesis and abstract principles, are able to make an accordance in their mind. In other words, in this phase children are able to read situation and predict the conclusion by making hypothesis.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Experimental research is used as a tool in this study for research. In this kind of research, program or treatment procedure is introduced intentionally and then results are focused through observation. American Heritage Dictionary defined experiment as "A test under controlled conditions that is made to demonstrate a known trust, which examine the validity of a hypothesis, or determine the efficacy of something previously untried".

In order to bring improvement and change in practice, it is reflective and evaluative. It provides cooperative collaboration with colleagues so it is a participatory research. Impetus for changes is provided by the collection of data or information.

There is rich tradition for experimental research in education and psychology. For over the past 40 years its usage has been influenced by the research practices in parent discipline or theory development. Application process and systematic planning has always been facilitated by experiments conducting.

Consistent trends are being shown over the last five decades for using experimental tool in educational technology and are reflected by ETR & D publications. Related to descriptive studies, quasi experiments, and time series designs many frequent experiments have been conducted over the years. Though, external or internal greater balancing validity has been demonstrated over time by the increased use of stimulated and realistic materials in experiments.

It can be concluded from above description that for improvement related to educational problems and to overcome them, systematic study of experimental research is done. It's done by the collaboration of researchers, teachers, and those interested in problem of affected by it by means of their own practical actions and by means of their own reflection upon the effect of the experiments. The research conducted in this study was about teaching vocabulary to the fourth graders. Teacher and researcher collaborated together to conduct research using realia. Experimental research was done to incorporate the realia technique in vocabulary teaching. During this experiment the researcher acted as a teacher while the teacher acted as an observer.**Place and Time of Research:**

This experimental research was carried out at one of the private schools (Arabian-e-Sophia School, Lahore). The research was conducted in 2018.

Population and Sampling:

Students studying in fourth grade in year 2017 – 2018 at a private school named, Arabian e Sophia were used as a subject of study. Almost 20 numbers of active students were there in the class. Students liked talking and playing and they were average achievers academically. No student needed any extra attention in their studies and they belonged to the middle-class background. Parents of majority students were employees in private or government organizations or some were entrepreneurs.

Tools:

Pretests and post tests were used as a collective data in this research. Moreover, to measure the vocabulary learning of students, written tests were used as a task. The evaluation was conducted after the teaching for the whole month when the post test was taken.

The Model of Research:

Model made by Kempis & Mc Taggart was used for the experimental research in the study. Kempis and Taggart used system of spirals with any cycles in this model. Moreover, each cycle consists of four steps. 1) Planning 2) Action 3) Observation 4) Reflection. The model can be demonstrated like this:

The procedure of Research:

The cycle consists of four steps and the research procedure for each step is as follows:

Planning:

The researcher performed pre-research observation before the implementation of experimental research. During research, the teaching process conducted by the English teacher was keenly observed by the researcher. She then interviewed the class students along with the teacher to better know their condition while learning English. During interview and observations, some problems related to students while mastering vocabulary came to the surface. There is a difficulty for students in remembering vocabulary words and their meanings. Moreover, they also face difficulty while writing the words correctly. In addition to that, they also face difficulty in pronouncing those words. Besides, they were totally not taking interest in following the learning process taught by the teacher. So, by keeping in mind all these problems, it was suggested to use realia technique in teaching.

Pre and post tests were conducted by researchers. In order to test the current knowledge of student's English vocabulary, pre-test was conducted. Moreover, post-test was conducted to know about the improvements that will come in students to master vocabulary after the conducting the experiment. At the end of each cycle the test was conducted. Both the pre and post tests were compared to get to know about the improvement student achieved in before and after the implementation of experiment.

Next step was to make lesson plans for students by discussing the content with English teacher so that it can be implemented in the class.

“Shape & things” was the topic chosen and designed by the researcher to implement the related activities in the classroom. Furthermore, teaching aids like ball, coin, box, chalk, money, geometrically cut papers and many other objects available in classroom were prepared by the researcher. She also arranged digital camera, students list and observation sheet.

Implementing the Experiment:

The technique was implemented in the class during this step. Researcher became a teacher herself this time in the class. During the research realia technique was used in teaching students the learning new vocabulary according to the lesson plan based on teaching procedures and learning aids. Various activities were done by researchers to implement the experiment. Topics were presented, tasks were given and the evaluation was done.

a. Presenting the topic:

In every cycle, one topic was presented by the researcher. Sound meanings were covered in the presentation i.e. introduction of new words, their meanings and pronunciation, illustrative sentences and focus on simple grammar, teaching aids and text books were used by researchers to deal with the topic.

b. Giving Task:

Students were given some tasks by the researcher and the students have to do the activities using the material provided by the teacher. Exercise, practices, homework and different discussions were done.

c. Evaluation:

Pretests and post tests were given by the researcher. These tests were given in every cycle to the students. Before the experiment pre-test was taken and after the experiment post test was conducted.

Observation:

During the process of learning and teaching all the activities performed were observed keenly by the researcher. Along with the results of pretests and posttests the events happened in the classroom were also observed by the researcher.

Reflection:

Reflection was made by using the collected data in the previous step. Through this collected data strengths and weaknesses were identified, results were analyzed and the conclusion was drawn. This analysis of the result further in this research worked as a main consideration for the other experiment.

Collecting the Data:

Tests technique was used to collect data. They were of two kinds; the first one was pre-test and the second one was post-test. They occur in every cycle as the pre-test was used for the current knowledge of the student while that post-test was to know the results of the implementation of experiment. One of them was conducted before the experiment and other at the end after the implementation. However, the test items remain the same for the same single cycle. It contains various MCQs and its result was examined to judge the improvement happened in student's vocabulary.

Technique of Data Procedure:

The experimental research done in this study at classroom was taken as a success. Students mastering vocabulary also got improvement. So, the results were very well achieved using the realia technique in teaching. Pretests and post tests were used to collect quantitative data used in this study and its results were statistically analyzed.

The test results were analyzed by finding mean value of both tests. The results were used to analyze the performance before and after the implementation of experiment and to analyze the teaching and learning results.

The mean score of pre-test and post-test can be calculated with the formula as follows:

$$\bar{X} = \frac{X}{N} \quad \bar{Y} = \frac{Y}{N}$$

In which:

- X = Means of pre-test score
- Y = Means of post-test score
- N = numbers of sample.

Data Analysis

Before starting with the analysis and the interpretation of the pre and posttest; it is necessary to say that this study was carried out in a unique experimental group; it means that there was no control group. Besides considering teachers academic availability, this study was developed in one month. Moreover, it is necessary to say that each academic hour lasts around 30 minutes.

To start with the pre-test results, analysis it is important to explain the aim of the pre-test. It was to diagnose the students' English knowledge and to know the concrete English vocabulary knowledge that the students had before the application of the treatment. So, according to the chapter III, it is mentioned that after the treatment the researcher made, it was necessary to apply the post-test to know if there was a positive or negative influence in concrete vocabulary learning using realia.

The following graphs show the quantitative results from the study. First of all, it is essential to show the results from the pre and post-test. Afterwards a comparison of both.

Those results were obtained after having revised the pre and post-test.

Comparison of the pre-test and the post test.

To continue with the process of this research, this project shows the comparison of the pre-test and post-test results in the following tables.

Table 1: Comparison of the pre and post-test, fruits and vegetables.

Analyzing the student's pre-test result we noticed that they had prior about those items. After the application of the treatment using realia, "the fruit and vegetable items" during the activity the students touched, smelled, ate and felt some of them. It helped students to learn in a better way. Taking into account the graph above, the item they learned the most was the melon fruit. They learned it easier because its yellow color was attractive for them and most of them liked it. And the vegetable they learn the most was the potato. It could be because the majority of the students liked it very much.

The graph above shows the pre-test percentage had greatly increased after treatment and in post-test percentage is greater than pre-test.

The graph above shows the pre-test, 10% to 50% of the students had knowledge about those items. In the post-test shows 50% to 98% of the students answered correctly. It means that realia worked significantly with those types of items.

Table 2: Comparison of the pre and post-test, Sports.

Analyzing the students' pre-test results, we observed that they had knowledge about those items because the graph showed it. After having applied the treatment using the sport items and the students played them, we observed that the students in this activity had the direct contact with the sports, objects. Therefore, this was the reason why the students demonstrated the expected results.

The graph above, we can observe that in the pre-test, 30% to 63.5% of the students answered all the items correctly. It means that students had a good knowledge about those items in the post-test 35% to 65.5% of the students showed an improvement but not as we expected.

Table 3: Comparison of the pre and post-test, verbs.

In the graph above, the students made an improvement in some verb such as: to clean, to jump, to eat, to drink. The above graph shows that in the pre-test 40% of the students answered the verb “to clean” correctly and in the post-test, this item shows that 75% of the students answered it correctly. The students recognized the word and the picture. Furthermore, the verbs, “to jump”, “to eat”, “to drink” also showed good results. In the post-test 86.5% of the students answered the verb “to jump” correctly, 89.5 of the students answered the verb “to eat” correctly, and 80% of the students the verb “to drink” correctly. The verb “to eat” is answered by the students most correctly. It could be because the students associated it with the first topic, which were fruits and vegetables. So, in this activity, they saw those fruits which the teacher was pretending to bite. That is why most of the students learned the verb “to eat” successfully. We can say that those verbs worked positively because the students performed the actions.

However, with the items “to drop” and “to cook” the results were not as expected. Comparing the pre and the post-test results, these verbs have not that much positive result as expected. It could be that the students did not pay attention at the time when teacher was performing action. Therefore, the students could be confused.

Table 4: Comparison of the pre and post-test, Clothes.

Finally, in the graph above, the treatment using realia worked in the expected way. All of the items presented a significant improvement. 80.5% of the students in the post-test results answered “Cap” correctly, 83% answered “Pants” correctly, showing highest percentage. It could be the topic was interesting for the students; they were exciting to see the garment which the teacher had brought to the classroom. Therefore, all of the items in the pre-test were lower as compare to the post-test results which were higher. It could be so that students were involved in the activities done in the classroom; they were having direct contact with all the cloths and fully involved in the activity.

Table: 5 Comparison of the pre and post-test, birds

After analyzing the students' pretest results it was observed that they were aware of those items. Excellent performance of the student was observed after the proper treatment of Realia. statistical figures on the bar chart are indicating of their learning spirit, because of their excellent schemata the results of post tests were improved as compared to result of pre-test after analyzing the students pre-test results, it was observed that were aware of those items.

From the above graph we can observe that in the pre-test 45 % to 50 % of the students answered all the items correctly. It means that student has a good knowledge about those items in the post-test 57 % to 80 % of the students showed an improvement.

Table: 6 Comparison of the pre and post-test, animals.

In the above the treatment using Realia showed again improvement. All these items presented a significant improvement. 70 % of the students in the post-test result answered "Goat" correctly, 80 % answered correctly "Buffalo" 75 % answered "Cow" correctly, 50 % answered correctly. Realia showed greater improvement.

Comparison of Pre-test and Post-test, Fruits & Vegetables

Table No:1

Names	Marks Total	Marks Pre-test	Marks post-test	Percentage	
				Pre-test	Post-test
Cherry	10	1	7	10%	70%
Plum	10	3.7	8	37%	80%
Melon	10	3.5	8.4	35%	84%
Strawberry	10	2	6.5	20%	65%
Water Melon	10	1.8	7.8	18%	78%
Carrot	10	2	9	20%	90%
Potato	10	4	9.9	40%	99%
Tomato	10	4.9	8.6	49%	86%
Onion	10	4.5	9.6	45%	96%
Garlic	10	1.96	7.9	19.6%	79%

Comparison of Pre-test and Post-test, Sports

Table No:2

Names	Marks Total	Marks Pre-test	Marks post-test	Percentage	
				Pre-test	Post-test
Cricket	10	7	9	70%	90%
Hockey	10	6.5	8.8	65%	88%
Football	10	6	8.6	60%	86%
Basket Ball	10	4.1	8	41%	80%
Table Tennis	10	2.7	7.6	27%	76%

Comparison of Pre-test and Post-test, verbs

Table No:3

Names	Marks Total	Marks Pre-test	Marks post-test	Percentage	
				Pre-test	Post-test
To drop	10	2.5	6	25%	60%
To clean	10	4	7.6	40%	76%
To jump	10	4.5	8.8	45%	88%
To eat	10	3.1	9	31%	90%
To drink	10	4.5	8	45%	80%
To cook	10	4.6	6.4	46%	64%

Comparison of Pre-test and Post-test, Clothes

Table No:4

Names	Marks Total	Marks Pre-test	Marks post-test	Percentage	
				Pre-test	Post-test
Shoes	10	2.1	7.9	21%	79%
Socks	10	1.5	6	15%	60%
Cap	10	1.2	8	12%	80%
Belt	10	1	5	10%	50%
T. shirt	10	1.7	3.4	17%	34%
Jacket	10	1.7	3	17%	30%
Pants	10	1.5	8.3	15%	83%

Comparison of Pre-test and Post-test, birds

Table No:5

Names	Marks Total	Marks Pre-test	Marks post-test	Percentage	
				Pre-test	Post-test
Sparrow	10	4.5	7.5	45%	75%
Parrot	10	5	8	50%	80%
Crow	10	4	6.7	40%	57%
Nightingale	10	2	5	20%	50%
Pigeon	10	4	8	40%	80%

Comparison of Pre-test and Post-test, animal
Table No:6

Names	Marks Total	Marks Pre-test	Marks post-test	Percentage	
				Pre-test	Post-test
Cow	10	3.8	7.5	38%	75%
Goat	10	5	8.5	50%	85%
Buff allow	10	4	8	40%	80%
Deer	10	2	5	20%	50%
Lion	10	4	7	40%	70%

CONCLUSION, FINDINGS AND SUGGESTIONS

Conclusion:

After having diagnosed, applied and gotten the results of the treatment following conclusions were embodied. The use of realia in order to improve the students' vocabulary proficiency for finding the meaning of words was the basic object of research. No doubt, use of realia makes it effective for the students to remember vocabularies in an easier way. In various activities the improvement of result of pre-test and post-test after the implementation of realia can easily be observed. That clearly showed the importance of use of realia. No doubt the students learning capabilities were improved but in the condition of certain action some weaknesses were seen. The student could not be controlled easily by the teacher at the earlier stage. When the students were doing assignment in group, the class situation was noisy. Moreover, students were not able to concentrate over the lesson. They ignored their basic goal assigned by the teacher rather they got interested in learning activities and objects. Learning activities became a game for the students. The vocabularies interpreted through activity were ignored by them and they just got indulged in completing the game. The class was dominated by the naughty and clever students. Some students were not ready to cooperate with the group fellow while doing the activity. They observed only at the working of their fellows.

The researcher changed the activities form in order to eradicate the problem, such as the work was given individually through matching and guessing activities. Aim of this activity is to provoke the students' thinking capability and writing. Better results were obtained with the change of learning activity. The students did not depend always on their friends and teacher, rather they were more independent, due to which the process of learning and teaching run more smoothly. The lesson was paid more attention by the students. All the students participated actively. The clever students dominated the class again. Moreover, in learning, students' attitude positively progressed. In the classroom activities the students behaved in a disciplined manner. It became easy to control the students. During the implementation of the treatment, when the obtained results were taken into account, keeping in view the hypothesis we gained expected results and the goals were achieved because of evidence of concrete learning of vocabulary was shown through the results. The effects of the lesson's plans, analysis and creation were the objectives, followed systematically by the researcher. Best activities were selected by the researcher for the young learners and they showed improvement, which was depicted by the graphs. The lesson plans about fruit, vegetables, sports, verb did work and the results showed an improvement.

The application of the lesson plans for concrete vocabulary learning using realia worked positively with some items such as: fruit, vegetables, verbs, sports, and cloths because the students touched, smelled, etc., and felt some of them so, the students were engaged with the activities. However, some of the items did not work appropriately. The treatment did not work successfully with some items because somewhat the students did not understand the concept that items showed. As conclusion, the use of realia to teach concrete vocabulary worked with some items and with other topics not so much because there are some aspects that influence vocabulary learning. Those aspects are important because they stimulate explicit learning. It means that concrete vocabulary teaching and realia can be associated at the moment of teaching because the students can make conscious efforts to notice new lexical items and selective attending. However, there other features that could influence the concrete vocabulary learning so we did not obtain significant results. For example: enthusiasm, attitudes towards vocabulary learning, fear of failure and same attitude to learn a foreign language.

Besides taking into account the results of the fruits and vegetables, it can be said that concrete vocabulary is an adequate topic to be brought using realia. One reason is that during the activities, the students were discovering the objects. So, they were expecting to know what things were there, and to guess how to pronounce and write them in English. Therefore, it helps the students to be attentive and to learn through discovery using real materials. The results showed an improvement in learning concrete vocabulary about fruits and vegetables. Taking into account the results obtained in the sports item, there was a great difference between before and after using realia.

In the verb items, the students showed an improvement taking into account the percentage of the tests. Therefore, in learning concrete vocabulary using realia, there is an improvement related to verbs because more than half of the students answered the half of the items; considering this as a progress. This treatment gave the expected results because all students were performing each verb.

Further taking into account the comparison chart about clothes, the improvement in students learning is evident. So, using realia with this topic provided significant results. The knowledge that the students had before the treatment was not relevant. However, it helped as a basis to work with the students and the result of the post-test showed an improvement in learning concrete vocabulary. The students were engaged in the activities. The students had the opportunity to touch each article of clothing and see their own clothes, too.

According to the research-based findings it was concluded by the researcher the use of realia in English teaching may improve students' credulity specially in case of mastering vocabulary of English language. In learning the students' attitude also changes due to this. The students were well motivated, active and started paying attention due to the implementation of realia.

Suggestions

Based on the research findings, the researcher suggested for English teacher, students, institutions and other researchers.

To the teacher

It is important for the teacher to select the suitable methodology in vocabulary teaching for children. Teaching English needs to make a healthy atmosphere in the classroom consequently the process of teaching and learning becomes easy, enjoyable and interesting. The teaching methodology that is adopted by the teacher is use of realia. In order to make the learning easier, full of fun and interesting, realia can be used by the teacher. The implementation of realia can be accompanied with some activities related to learning such as games, guessing and matching activity and group work. Concept of vocabulary strengthens with realia because it relates the vocabulary with the objects directly. Resultantly, the memorization of the vocabulary meaning becomes easier to the students with the help of realia.

To the students

In English learning the students should be active and in there must be no dependency. English learning should be continuous and intensive. The things in the surroundings can be used by the students by fixing labels on the things along with the words that deals with that thing such as name of that thing. So, it becomes easy for the students to memorize the words that deal with the things in English language.

To the researcher

The current research clarifies the implementation of realia in vocabulary teaching at elementary level. This study shows how the use of realia strengthens the motivation and achievement of students in English learning. The result of the research is hoped to be proved useful as the additional reference to do more structural and explorative research about the effectivity of realia at other levels and topics in English teaching.

To the educational institute

The educational institute is considered to be formal place for education and knowledge learning. The research result is one way to have more information about the situation and problems of teaching learning process in school. Having the knowledge of such conditions, the school will improve the education effectively. Another way is by improving the teacher quality. There must be a space for the teacher in the institute by facilitating him good teaching and learning equipment, providing teachers to join research and different training programmers. It means that concrete vocabulary teaching and realia can be associated at the moment of teaching because the students can make conscious efforts to notice new lexical items and selective attending. Nevertheless, there are other features that influence the vocabulary learning process. For example, enthusiasm, attitudes towards vocabulary learning, fear of failure and the same attitude to learn foreign language. So, the learning of new items in English is pulled by the aspects mentioned before.

References

- AL Qahtani, M. (2015). The importance of vocabulary in language learning and how to be taught. *International journal of teaching and education*, 3(3), 21-34.
- Collier, V. P. (1987). Age and rate of acquisition of second language for academic purposes. *TESOL quarterly*, 21(4), 617-641.
- Coxhead, A. (2000). A new academic word list. *TESOL quarterly*, 34(2), 213-238.
- De Jong, E. J., & Harper, C. A. (2005). Preparing mainstream teachers for English-language learners: Is being a good teacher good enough? *Teacher Education Quarterly*, 32(2), 101-124.
- Ehrman, M., & Oxford, R. (1990). Adult language learning styles and strategies in an intensive training setting. *The modern language journal*, 74(3), 311-327.
- Gottfredson, L. S. (1981). Circumscription and compromise: A developmental theory of occupational aspirations. *Journal of Counseling psychology*, 28(6), 545.
- Hirsch, E. D. (2003). Reading comprehension requires knowledge—of words and the world. *American Educator*, 27(1), 10-13.
- Hutto, D. D. (2005). Knowing what? Radical versus conservative enactivism. *Phenomenology and the Cognitive Sciences*, 4(4), 389-405.

- Jackendoff, R. (1999). Possible stages in the evolution of the language capacity. *Trends in cognitive sciences*, 3(7), 272-279.
- Miller, G. A. (1995). WordNet: a lexical database for English. *Communications of the ACM*, 38(11), 39-41.
- Malcolm, N. (1954). Wittgenstein's Philosophical investigations. *The Philosophical Review*, 63(4), 530-559.
- Pearson, P. D., Hiebert, E. H., & Kamil, M. L. (2007). Vocabulary assessment: What we know and what we need to learn. *Reading research quarterly*, 42(2), 282-296.
- Resnick, L. B. (1987). The 1987 presidential address learning in school and out. *Educational researcher*, 16(9), 13-54.
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